

Oxidation reactions catalysed by polymer anchored transition metal complexes

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Abstract : Polymer-anchored transition metal complexes were synthesized by supporting cobalt, iron and copper on cation exchange resin (polystyrene). The catalysts were characterized by CHN analysis, SEM, IR spectroscopy, ESR and thermal studies. The catalysts were found to be active for oxidation of some alcohols under mild conditions of temperature and pressure. The influence of polarity of solvent on the rate of reaction was studied. The rate of oxidation was influenced by the concentration of catalyst and substrate as well. The catalysts retain the same efficiency for 5–6 runs.

Keywords : Polymer-anchored catalysts, oxidation, molecular oxygen, recycling efficiency.

Introduction

The use of polymer-supports in organic reactions has emerged as an attractive approach in both fundamental and technological field¹⁻³. Simplification of work up procedure, automation, facile access to the active site by soluble reagents and the reusability of the active sites are some of the significant advantages that these systems can offer. Polymer anchored reagents are used as oxidising agents, reducing agents, photosensitisers and active reagents in agriculture and pharmacology⁴⁻⁶. The application of polymer bound metal complexes as catalysts are quite attractive because they can be applied to industrial exploitation. Polystyrene is widely used as a versatile support because a wide range of functional groups can be incorporated on it.

Oxidation using molecular oxygen as the oxidant catalysed by transition metal complexes provides an attractive route for the preparation of synthetic intermediates without the use of environmentally hazardous oxidants^{7,8}.

In this paper we report oxidation of some alcohols using polymer-anchored cobalt(II), iron(III) and copper(II) complexes using molecular oxygen as the oxidant.

Results and discussion

The elemental analytical data are presented in the Table 1 for the catalysts prepared using cobalt(II), iron(III) and copper(II) [catalysts I, II and III respectively]. The data indicate the incorporation of the metals into the polymer matrix. The metal contents of the catalysts were 13.3,

11.6 and 11.8 milligrams of the respective metals per gram of the catalyst as determined by spectrophotometry by standard methods⁹.

Table 1. Elemental analysis of catalysts in wt %

	Polymer support		After complexation	
	C	H	C	H
Catalyst I	84.68	8.26	84.11	7.96
Catalyst II	84.68	8.26	84.13	7.91
Catalyst III	84.68	8.26	84.12	7.94

The micrographs obtained from the Scanning Electron Microscope are presented in Figs. 1a to 1d and their EDS are given in Figs. 2a to 2d. From the changes in the

Fig. 1a. Polymer support.

Fig. 1b. After complexation with Co^{II}.

Fig. 1c. After complexation with Fe^{III}.

Fig. 1d. After complexation with Cu^{II}.

Fig. 2a. Polymer support.

Fig. 2b. After complexation with Co^{II}.

Fig. 2c. After complexation with Fe^{III}.

 Fig. 2d. After complexation with Cu^{II} .

morphology of the catalysts, the attachment of the metals to the polymer matrix has been confirmed.

The IR spectra of the catalysts show the relevant bands confirming the attachment of the metals to the polymer support.

From the ESR spectra, the parameters g_{\parallel} and g_{\perp} calculated by Kneubuhl¹⁰ method are presented in Table 3. Since the g_{\parallel} values are less than 2.3, a covalent charac-

ter can be attributed to the metal-ligand bond. For the catalyst with cobalt(II), no ESR signal was observed. This observation can be attributed to the rapid spin-lattice relaxation or due to the oxidation to cobalt(III) state¹².

All the three catalysts were found to be stable up to a temperature of 300 °C by TGA studies.

The rates of oxidation for various alcohols using the three catalysts are presented in Table 4. The rate of reaction is higher for terminal alcohols than secondary alcohols. Aliphatic alcohols are getting oxidized at higher rates when compared with aromatic alcohols.

The rates of reaction increase linearly on increasing the concentration of both the catalyst as well as the substrate, indicating the first order dependence of the rate on the concentrations of both the catalyst and substrate.

Rate of reaction \propto [Catalyst] [Substrate] :

Effect of solvent polarity on rate of oxidation :

Benzyl alcohol was oxygenated in a wide range of

Table 2. IR bands of the catalysts

Band (cm^{-1})	Assignment
1033	$-\text{SO}_3^-$
300	Co-Cl
296	Fe-Cl
293	Cu-Cl

Table 3. EPR parameters for catalysts II and III

Catalyst	Temperature	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}
Fe^{III}	LNT	2.10	2.09
Cu^{II}	LNT	2.06	2.04

Table 4. Rates of oxidation for various alcohols at 35 °C and atm. pressure

Substrate (0.2 M)	Rate $\times 10^3 = M \text{ min}^{-1}$		
	(Catalyst I) $\times 10^3$	(Catalyst II) $\times 10^3$	(Catalyst III) $\times 10^3$
<i>n</i> -Butanol	0.89	0.77	0.71
<i>n</i> -Hexanol	0.81	0.68	0.65
Benzyl alcohol	0.79	0.60	0.61
2-Propanol	0.72	0.53	0.48
2-Butanol	0.63	0.44	0.36

solvents with varying polarity and coordinating ability and swelling ability of cross linked polymer. The results have been summarized in the Table 5.

Table 5. Rates of oxidation for benzyl alcohol in various solvents
[Benzyl alcohol] = 0.3 M, [Catalyst-I] $\times 10^3 = 0.405$ M 35 °C

Solvent	Rate $\times 10^3$ (M min ⁻¹)
Methanol	0.75
Ethanol	0.52
Acetone	0.34
DMF	0.29
DMSO	0
Benzene	0.40
Toluene	0.50
Chlorobenzene	0.39
Cyclohexane	0.30
Carbon tetrachloride	0.26

Polar protic solvents such as alcohols favour the reaction. The highest rate of reaction is observed in methanol because of its polar nature¹³. Acetone which is less polar and non-protic gives a lower rate. DMF retards the reaction by coordinating with the catalyst, even though it is polar. DMSO which coordinates strongly and irreversibly with the catalyst, does not allow the reaction to proceed. So the extent of coordinating capacity of the solvent with the metal plays a significant role in influencing the rate of reaction apart from the polarity of the solvent¹⁴.

Among non-polar solvents the rates of reaction are lower in cyclohexane and carbon tetrachloride¹⁵. The rates of reaction are enhanced by benzene and toluene because they can swell the polymer beads. Thus the reaction in benzene and toluene are higher than in the case of non-polar solvents due to the increase in the availability of catalytic sites¹⁶. Since the highest rate is observed in methanol, it can be concluded that in the present investigation polarity of the medium overrides the effects due to swelling of the polymer beads.

Oxidation of benzyl alcohol and 2-butanol in toluene-methanol mixtures :

Benzyl alcohol and 2-butanol were oxygenated in toluene-methanol mixture of various compositions by volume. In all the cases the concentration of the catalyst I and substrate were kept constant. For both the substrates the rates of reaction increase on increasing the percen-

tage of methanol. So it can be concluded that the rate of reaction is more influenced by the polarity of the medium in the present study. The results are shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Effect of solvent polarity on the initial rate of oxidation for benzyl alcohol and 2-butanol.

Product analysis :

The formation of the corresponding carbonyl compounds were detected with 70–80% yield for the oxidation of the alcohols by GLC analysis using FFAP column in NUCON chromatograph with a thermal conductivity detector. Identifications were done by comparing the retention times with those of authentic samples. No other side products were detected.

Recycling efficiency :

It is found that the catalysts were recyclable upto six runs with the same reaction rates. Afterwards the rate of reaction decreased gradually. The loss of catalytic activity may be due to the loss of mechanical strength of the polymer and also due to metal leaching¹⁷.

Experimental

All the solvents and substrates were purified by standard methods. AnalaR samples of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, FeCl_3 and $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ supplied by Fischer Chemicals were used as such. Styrene-divinylbenzene 225 resin (cation exchange resin) was supplied by Ion Exchange India Ltd. Commercial oxygen was purified by passing through copper gauze maintained at 250 °C and dried over molecular sieve.

Preparation of the catalysts :

A mixture of the polymer resin and the metal chlorides were stirred in absolute ethanol for 24 h. The resulting beads were filtered, washed with absolute ethanol and dried under vacuum.

Experimental set-up :

The oxidation reactions were carried out at room temperature in a static reactor using molecular oxygen as the oxidant at one atmospheric pressure. The catalyst was taken inside the reaction vessel and connected to the reaction set-up. Then the entire system was evacuated and oxygen gas was introduced into it. The substrate along with the solvent were introduced into the reaction vessel through a rubber septum. The kinetics of reaction was followed by the uptake of oxygen using a gas burette filled with liquid paraffin as a function of time. The oxidation reactions were carried out in methanol-toluene mixture (1 : 1 by volume). Blank experiments were carried out in the absence of catalyst as well as the substrate. In both the cases there was no uptake of oxygen. So the reaction did not proceed in both the cases.

Conclusion :

The polymer-anchored transition metal complexes are found to be efficient catalysts for oxidation of alcoholic substrates under mild conditions of temperature and pressure satisfying the conditions of green chemistry.

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